

Title: Diving into the microstructural tailoring of eco-friendly refractory aggregates

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On the rising demand for eco-friendly refractories, challenges remain to be addressed, such as reducing the use of chromium-based aggregates. In this sense, Borges *et al.* proposed Cr-free alternative compositions through a compositionally complex design approach. Four of these compositions were experimentally produced in a lab-scale arc melter and the microstructural evaluation indicated the spinel precipitates' size and morphology differed significantly among them. In one case, the spinel was generated as a needle-like structure, whereas in the others, spherical-like precipitates with fine diameters were obtained. Aiming to identify the mechanisms acting in the generation of spinel precipitates with distinct morphologies, this work applied micro characterization techniques – such as synchrotron X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy, and electron backscatter diffraction. In all studied systems, the matrix and precipitate showed shared crystallographic orientation along the grains, leading to the formation of cube-to-cube interfaces due to the high unit-cell similarity between both phases. This, in turn, implies that the lattice parameter misfit will dictate the magnitude of the coherency strengths taking place within the interfaces. In this sense, higher absolute misfit values increase the interfacial energy between the phases, favoring the formation of spherical-like spinels to minimize the surface-to-volume ratio. In contrast, systems with lower misfit values will nucleate the precipitates along the lower energy planes and directions, resulting in the formation of a continuous 3D networks of spinel precipitates along the MgO-based aggregate. Nevertheless, the precipitate size in the eco-friendly aggregates was shown to be highly affected by kinetic factors, which were not addressed in this study. On top of that, this understanding of the described mechanisms can be a valuable tool to tailor the microstructure of other systems, which was demonstrated by changing the precipitate morphology from oblong to spherical through a minor addition (3 wt%) of Nb₂O₅. However, the laboratory electrofusion route – used

to produce the samples evaluated so far – halts the manufacture of specimens for macroscopic tests due to the small-scale production of the aggregates. Thus, with the aid of an industrial partner, alternative routes – and the impact of their use on the final properties of the obtained product – are under investigation.

Keywords: Magnesia-chromite; Spinel; Thermodynamics; EBSD; synchrotron XRD.

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